

Seroprevalence of Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E infection amongst clinically suspected cases of Acute Viral Hepatitis at tertiary care hospital, Jaipur Rajasthan

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ABSTRACT

Background: Viral hepatitis is a significant cause of morbidity in India and is now equated as a threat comparable to the ‘‘big three’’ communicable diseases viz. AIDS, malaria, and tuberculosis. The primary aim of present study was to determine the seroprevalence of Hepatitis A, Hepatitis E and co-infection amongst the patient’s suspected with signs and symptoms of acute viral hepatitis and also to determine the demographic pattern and seasonal distribution of viral hepatitis infection.

Material and Method: Two hundred fifty eight patients with symptoms of acute viral hepatitis were taken and single centre, hospital based, cross-sectional observational study was done over period of one year.**Result and Conclusion:** Out of 258 patients, HAV IgM antibody was detected in 33 patients (seroprevalence-12.7%), HEV IgM antibody was detected in 28 (seroprevalence-10.9%) and co-infection was detected in 6 patients (seroprevalence 2.3%). Seroprevalence of HAV was more common in males (57.60%) while of Hepatitis E Virus was more common in females (67.9%). Maximum number of patients of Hepatitis A virus were in age group 0-20 years while Hepatitis E virus were in age group 21-40 years. Majority of patients were residing in slum area (39.53%). Most of the cases were seen in months of August to October i.e. during monsoon season and were from low socioeconomic group who did not have facility for safe drinking water. A community programme like ‘‘Swatch Bharat Abhiyan’’ and other surveillance programme by hospitals with multipronged approach of screening are expected to reduce incidence of infected viral Hepatitis.

Keywords: Acute Hepatitis, Gastroenteritis, Seasonal Trend, Water borne diseases.

INTRODUCTION

Viral hepatitis is a significant cause of morbidity in India and is now equated as a threat comparable to the ‘‘big three’’ communicable diseases viz. AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis¹. The World Health Organization

estimates that there are 1.4 million cases of hepatitis A globally each year resulting in approximately 7000 deaths². In comparison, there are an estimated 20 million hepatitis E infections each year leading to 3.3 million symptomatic cases and around 44,000 death³. All cases of acute viral hepatitis are caused by one of five viral agents, among all the enteric pathogens i.e. Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E viruses are epidemiologically the most important ones⁴. Both viruses cause sporadic infections as well as epidemic outbreaks of acute viral hepatitis.

HAV spreads via the faecal-oral route and is associated with poor sanitary and bad hygienic conditions. HAV infection is common during childhood and usually results in mild anicteric hepatitis⁵. India is categorised as a hyper-endemic country for HAV because HAV is highly prevalent among the paediatric age groups as exposure to the Hepatitis A virus typically occurs early in life when the infection is often subclinical. HEV also primarily spread via the faeco-oral route and is an enterically transmitted pathogen like HAV⁶. HEV is the commonest causative agent of acute viral hepatitis and is responsible for epidemics, focal outbreaks as well as sporadic infections⁷. During an outbreak, it is observed that pregnant women have a higher likelihood of getting infected (12–20%) with HEV and have a higher propensity to develop acute liver failure (ALF) (10–22%) when compared to non-pregnant females (1–2%)⁸.

Exposure rate of HAV and HEV vary widely between different geographical regions, predominantly influenced by socioeconomic factors. Despite being a major health challenge, not many studies exploring the prevalence, aetiology, and clinic-epidemiological profile of acute viral hepatitis are available in India. Though few studies describing the incidence or aetiology of viral hepatitis have been reported from various parts of the country, there are not many studies conducted in the state of Rajasthan. The primary aim of present study was to determine the seroprevalence of Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E viruses among patients presenting with symptoms of acute viral

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hepatitis. In addition, the present study was conducted to determine the frequency, seasonal distribution, pattern of viral hepatitis infection, associated clinical features and outcome among clinically suspected acute viral hepatitis cases presented at SMS Hospital, Jaipur, Rajasthan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The present study was conducted in Central Laboratory of a Medical College and attached tertiary care Hospitals. The data collection was initiated after the research protocol was approved by the Institute's Ethical Committee. At the time of enrolment, informed written consent was obtained from participants and a performa was filled which consisted of socio-demographic characteristics & clinical history of study participants. The study was conducted over a period of one year from May 2021- April 2022. Two hundred fifty eight patients were enrolled in the study presenting with sign and symptoms of jaundice, fever, pain abdomen, dark urine, nausea and vomiting which were considered as suspected cases of acute viral hepatitis.

Sample Collection and Processing: 5ml of whole blood was collected by venepuncture into a sterile plain vial and allowed to clot. The clotted blood sample was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 10 minutes to obtain serum. The serum was then transferred into a separate tube and then stored at 2-8°C in refrigerator and tested by following methods.

- i. **HAV IgM antibody:** HAV IgM Antibody was detected by commercially available ELISA (BIONEOVAN Co. Ltd-China). Tests were performed in accordance with manufactures instruction.
- ii. **HEV IgM antibody:** HEV IgM Antibody was detected by commercially available ELISA (BIONEOVAN Co. Ltd-China). Tests were performed in accordance with manufactures instruction.

Statistical Analysis Plan: All the data were collected in a paper-based data collection form. Thereafter, the data were coded and entered in Microsoft Excel. The coded data were imported into Stata 17.1 version for analysis. For the continuous data, the mean, median, mode, and standard deviation was calculated.

RESULTS

Blood sample were collected from patients and tested. HAV IgM antibody was detected in 33 patients (12.7%), HEV IgM antibody was detected in 28(10.9%) and co-infection was detected in 6 patients (2.3%).

Among 33 patients tested positive for Hepatitis A, 19 (57.60%) were male and 14 (42.40%) were female ($P = 0.403$). The maximum number of patients of Hepatitis-A IgM antibody belonged to age group 11-20 years (39.4%) followed by 0-10 years (33.3%). Hepatitis-A IgM antibody was detected in younger age group (p -value = 0.001). In

subclinical infection, ingestion of contaminated food or water imported from endemic areas, and/or contamination linked to environmental reservoir may serve as a reason for paediatric age group susceptibility to infection.

Among 28 patients tested positive for Hepatitis E; 19 (67.90%) were female and 9 (32.1%) were male ($p=0.034$). Among the 28 participants tested for Hepatitis E: 60.7% were aged between 21-40 years, and 21.4% were aged between 41-60 years of age.

The difference in distribution of Hepatitis A ($p=0.02$) and Hepatitis E ($p=0.017$) patients as per their residence was statistically significant which correspond to more cases found in people residing in slum areas owing to poor sanitation.

Out of 33 HAV positive patients, high seroprevalence were observed in low socioeconomic status group 15 (45.50%) followed by 8 (24.20%) in low or middle socioeconomic status group. The distribution of HAV patients as per their socioeconomic status was statistically significant ($p=0.032$). Among the 28 HEV positive patients, high seroprevalence were analyzed in low socioeconomic status (SES) 12 (42.80%) followed by 8 (28.60%) low middle socioeconomic status. There was no statistically significant difference found in HEV according to socioeconomic status ($p=0.108$).

High seroprevalence of hepatitis A and hepatitis E was found in piped drinking water followed by tank drinking water but there was no statistically significant difference found according to the source of drinking water (HAV; $p=0.08$ and HEV; $p=0.095$).

As shown in Table 2, out of 33 HAV positive; majority of positive patients were found in month of September (8, 18.60%) and October (8, 17.78%) and out of 28 HEV positive; majority of positive patients were found in September (7, 16.28%) and August (6, 15.79%) which correlates with pre-monsoon season in India.

DISCUSSION

HAV and HEV type of viral Hepatitis emerged as a major concern regarding public health in developing nations, specifically where there are unsystematic waste management facilities and poor supply of safe drinking water.

In present study, HAV IgM antibodies were detected in 33 patients (seroprevalence-12.7%) whereas HEV IgM antibody were detected in 28 patients (seroprevalence-10.9%). HAV is considered as a most common cause of viral hepatitis on global basis and present study also reported higher prevalence of HAV in comparison to HEV and same observation was analysed by Joon A et al⁹, Agarwal M et al¹⁰, Agarwal S et al¹¹, Murhekar MV et al¹², Chatterjee S et al.¹³ and Patel P et al¹⁴. Variation in

seroprevalence of both HAV and HEV in different regions might be due to personal hygiene, sanitation, and sources of water supply. It may also be due to the type of diagnostic kit utilized by the testing laboratory. Although, antibodies against different strains may also vary in persistence. Out of all Hepatitis A patients, 19 (57.60%) were male and 14 (42.40%) were female ($P = 0.403$). Present study is similar to conducted by Joon A et al.⁹ prevalence of males 68% were more than females 32% which was also in line with results of studies conducted by Mittal et al.¹⁵, Antony and Celine¹⁶, Sarangi et al.¹⁷, Barrientos-Gutierrez et al.¹⁸, Manmohan et al.¹⁹, Al-Naaimi et al.²⁰, Kamal et al.²¹, Dhamdhare and Nadkarni²², and Mishra et al.²³ Maximum patients of Hepatitis A belonged to age group 11-20 years (39.4%) followed by 0-10 years (33.3%). The difference in distribution of age group among patients diagnosed with Hepatitis A was statistically significant ($p=0.001$). Like our findings, studies by Joon et al.⁹, Mittal et al.¹⁵, Sarangi et al.¹⁷, Arora et al.²⁴, Chandra et al.²⁵, and Sebastian et al.²⁶ also reported that acute Hepatitis A infection was predominantly seen among children or adolescent. However, studies by Antony and Celine¹⁶, Davaalkham et al.²⁷, and Arankalle et al.²⁸ reported a shift of HAV infection from paediatric population to adults, might be due to improved standard of living. Highest seroprevalence of HAV was analysed in lower socioeconomic status group patients (45.5%) followed by low middle socioeconomic status group patients (24.2%). The difference in distribution of HAV patients as per their socioeconomic status was statistically significant ($p=0.032$). Similar to our study, Rath CP et al.²⁹ reported that HAV exposure was also significantly high among low socioeconomic status patients 53.9% in comparison to high/middle socioeconomic status 33.3%. Ahmed M et al.³⁰ found significantly lower HAV seroprevalence in high socioeconomic status vs. low socioeconomic status populations (68.8 vs. 79.7%, $p < 0.05$). Our results are consistent with the study conducted by Rath CP et al.²⁹ i.e. maximum number of HAV and HEV patients belonged to lower socioeconomic status and lived in the area where sanitation facilities and water supply was inappropriate.²⁹

HEV IgM antibody were detected in 28 patients (seroprevalence -10.9%). Out of all 28 patients positive for Hepatitis E; 19 (67.90%) were female and 9 (32.1%) were male. Statistically significant difference was found according to gender ($P = 0.034$). Our results were consistent with Samadhar et al.³¹, Agarwal S et al.¹¹ and Bansal Y³² et al who also reported higher seroprevalence of HEV in female patients. Among the 28 patients tested for Hepatitis E: 60.70% were aged between 21-40 years,

and 21.43% were aged between 41-60 years of age. The HEV IgM antibodies were detected more in elder age groups. The difference in distribution of age group among patients diagnosed with Hepatitis E was statistically significant ($p=0.010$). Priyadarshini et al.³³ reported that the seropositivity of HEV in adults were (93.7%). Joon et al.⁹, Murhekar MV et al.¹², Mittal et al.¹⁵, Sarangi et al.¹⁷, Arora et al.²⁴, Chandra et al.²⁵, and Sebastian et al.²⁶ also reported HEV positivity was higher in patients more than 20 years which resembled the findings of present study. In the present study high seroprevalence of HEV was also noted from low socioeconomic status 42.80% followed by 28.60% low middle socioeconomic status. There is no statistically significant difference found in HEV according to socioeconomic status. ($p=0.108$).

The difference in distribution of HAV and HEV patients as per their residence was statistically significant ($p=0.02$ and $p=0.017$ respectively) and more among slum area residents.

In most positive patients of HAV (September 18.60% followed by October 17.78%, November 18.75%) and HEV (September 16.28%, October 11.11%, and November 12.50%) were seen near the time of monsoon season. Chatterjee S et al.¹³ reported that seasonal distribution of HAV and HEV infections followed a bimodal peak pattern with peaks reported in the pre-monsoon and rainy seasons. Kumar M et al.³⁴ reported that HAV cases were seen throughout the year with peaks of HAV cases in May, July and August and HEV cases in the month from January to May. Our results were consistent with Chatterjee S et al.¹³ and Samaddar A et al.³¹ who reported higher seroprevalence of HAV and HEV in pre-monsoon and rainy season.

Co-infection was detected in 6 patients (seroprevalence-2.3%). The rate of co-infection in present study was 2.3% which is in similar to a study done by Samaddar A et al.³¹ who reported co-infection in 2.07% of patients.

Figure 1: Distribution of patients according to seropositivity of HAV, HEV and Co infection

Table 1: Seroprevalence of HAV and HEV according to Demography and Socioeconomic status

Variable	Total Tested	HAV	HEV
		Positive Number (%)	Positive Number (%)
Gender			
Male	131	19 (57.6)	9 (32.1)
Female	127	14 (42.4)	19 (67.9)
Age Group			
0-10	54	11 (33.3)	1 (3.6)
11-20	51	13(39.4)	4 (14.3)
21-40	87	6 (18.2)	17 (60.7)
41-60	53	1 (3.0)	6 (21.4)
>60	13	2(6.0)	0 (0.0)
Residence			
Slum	102	19 (57.6)	18 (64.3)
Rural	85	11 (33.3)	6 (21.4)
Urban	71	3 (9.1)	4 (14.3)
p-value	-	0.020	0.017
Socioeconomic Status			
Upper Middle	48	3(9.1)	3(10.7)
Middle	72	7(21.2)	5(17.9)
Low Middle	73	8(24.2)	8(28.6)
Low	65	15(45.5)	12(42.8)
p-value	-	0.032	0.108
Source of Drinking water			
Bore-well	50	6(18.2)	6(21.4)
Piped	55	10(30.30)	8(28.6)
Tank	57	8(24.20)	6(21.4)
Handpump	52	6(18.2)	5(17.9)
Filtered	44	3(9.10)	3(10.7)
p-value	-	0.08	0.095

Table 2: Seroprevalence of HAV according to the time of year

Month	HAV Positive (N=33)		Total Number of patients tested
	Number of HAV positive patients	%	
May 21	1	7.69	13
June 21	2	10.00	20
July 21	3	11.11	27
August 21	6	15.79	38
September 21	8	18.60	43
October 21	8	17.78	45
November 21	3	18.75	16
December 21	1	5.56	18
January 22	0	0.00	8
February 22	0	0.00	8
March 22	0	0.00	10
April 22	1	8.33	12
Total	33		258

Table 3: Seroprevalence of HEV according to the time of year

Month	HEV Positive (N=28)		Total Number of patients tested
	Number of HEV positive Patients	%	
May 21	1	7.69	13
June 21	1	5.00	20
July 21	3	11.11	27
August 21	6	15.79	38
September 21	7	16.28	43
October 21	5	11.11	45
November 21	2	12.50	16
December 21	1	5.56	18
January 22	0	0.00	8
February 22	0	0.00	8
March 22	1	10.00	10
April 22	1	8.33	12
Total	28		258

CONCLUSION

Role of vaccination plays a vital role as this study shows high prevalence of HAV among children and low in adults. Purpose of study clearly indicate that Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E are preventable diseases as more cases were found from people residing in slum areas with poor water supply, hence improving sanitation can aid in prevention and it may lead to grave consequences, especially in pregnant women, so screening protocols should be set up for all pregnant females as part of the antenatal management for early detection of the cases.

The incidence of both Hepatitis A and E showed seasonal trend with highest cases detected around the time of monsoon and lowest during the winter and spring season. Public health problems associated with the faeco-oral transmission of viral hepatitis requires implementation of stronger measures to prevent faecal contamination of food and water.

A community program like “Swatchh Bharat Abhiyan” and a surveillance program by hospitals with multipronged approach of screening, treatment and immunization are expected to reduce incidences of infective viral hepatitis.

REFERENCES

1. Locarnini S, Chen D-S, Shibuya K. No more excuses: Viral hepatitis can be eliminated. Lancet. 2016; 387:1703–4.
2. World Health Organisation Hepatitis A fact sheet. 2020. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-a>
3. World Health Organisation Hepatitis E fact sheet. 2020. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hepatitis-e>

4. Verma R., Khanna P. Hepatitis A vaccine should receive priority in National Immunization Schedule in India. *Hum Vaccines Immunother.* 2012;8(8):1132–1134. doi: 10.4161/hv.20475.
5. *Damjanov I. The Hepatobiliary System. Pathology Secrets. 2009 Jan;1:263.*
6. Viral Hepatitis: Governmental efforts for its Control and Management. Available from: <https://pib.gov.in/newsite/printrelease.aspx?relid=168787>
7. World Health Organization. Prevention and Control of viral Hepatitis Infection: Framework for Global Action. World Health Organization. 2012. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/prevention-and-control-of-viral-hepatitis-infection-framework-for-global-action>
8. Acharya S.K., Madan K., Dattagupta S., Panda S.K. Viral hepatitis in India. *Natl Med J India.* 2006; 19(4):203–17.
9. Joon A, Rao P, Shenoy SM, Baliga S. Prevalence of Hepatitis A virus (HAV) and Hepatitis e virus (HEV) in the patients presenting with acute viral hepatitis. *Indian J Med Microbiol.* 2015;33:S102–5.
10. Agrawal M, Ruchi K, Ashish B, Pallab S. A Study of Seroprevalence and Co-infection of Hepatitis A and Hepatitis E Viruses in Sporadic Cases in an Endemic Area. *J Med Sci Heal.* 2016;02(03):1–5.
11. Agarwal S, Anuradha, Sahoo A, Duggal N. Seroprevalence of hepatitis a virus (HAV) and hepatitis E virus (HEV) Co-infection in the patients presenting with acute viral hepatitis attending a tertiary care hospital in north India. *J Commun Dis.* 2017;49(3):57–60.
12. Murhekar M V., Ashok M, Kanagasabai K, Joshua V, Ravi M, Sabarinathan R, et al. Epidemiology of hepatitis a and Hepatitis E based on laboratory surveillance data-India, 2014-2017. *Am J Trop Med Hyg.* 2018;99(4):1058–61.
13. Chatterjee S, Haldar J, Dutta P, Adak R, Ray R, Raj HJ, et al. Prevalence of Hepatitis a and Hepatitis E in West Bengal India- a Tertiary Care Hospital Based Study. *J Evol Med Dent Sci.* 2019;8(29):2341–6.
14. Patel P, Sood N, Modi D, Bhavsar HK. Prevalence of Hepatitis A Virus and Hepatitis E Virus Infection in Patients from A Tertiary Care Hospital of West India, Ahmedabad. *Saudi J Pathol Microbiol Abbreviated Key Title Saudi J Pathol Microbiol [Internet].* 2019
15. A Mittal R Bithu N Vyas RK Maheshwari Prevalence of hepatitis A virus and hepatitis E virus in the patients presenting with acute viral hepatitis at a tertiary care hospital Jaipur RajasthanN Niger J Clin Res201654750
16. Antony J, Celine TM. A hospital-based retrospective study on frequency and distribution of viral hepatitis. *J Global Infect Dis* 2014; 6:99–104.
17. Sarangi G, Dash M, Mahapatra D, Paty BP, Mohanty DP, Chayani N. Fecal-oral-transmitted hepatitis A and E prevalence in Eastern India: a 3-yr retrospective study. *J Med Soc* 2019; 33:86–90.
18. Barrientos-Gutierrez T, Brizuela-Alcantara D, Chavez-Tapia NC. Hepatitis A virus infection in high risk subjects. *Ann Hepatol* 2011; 10:578–9.
19. Manmohan G, Patil R, Khan MI, Gupta SK. Retrospective hospital based study of infective cases of jaundice in Tamil Nadu. *India Calicut Med J* 2011; 9:1–4.
20. Al-Naaimi AS, Turkey AM, Khaleel HA, Jalil RW, Mekhlef OA, Kareem SA, et al. Predicting acute viral hepatitis serum markers (A and E) in patients with suspected acute viral hepatitis attending primary health care centers in Baghdad: a one year cross-sectional study. *Global J Health Sci* 2012; 4:172–83.
21. Kamal SM, Mahmoud S, Hafez T, El-Fouly R. Viral hepatitis A to E in South Mediterranean countries. *Medit J Hemat Infect Dis* 2010; 2:e2010001.
22. Dhamdhare MR, Nadkarni MG. Infectious hepatitis at Aurangabad. Report of an outbreak. *Indian J Med Sci* 1962; 16:1006–15.
23. Mishra B, Srinivasa H, Muralidharan S, Charles S, Macaden RS. A hospital based study of hepatitis E by serology. *Indian J Med Microbiol* 2003; 21:115–7.
24. Arora D, Jindal N, Shukla RK, Bansal R. Waterborne hepatitis A and hepatitis E in Malwa region of Punjab, India. *J Clin Diagn Res* 2013; 7:2163–6.
25. Chandra NS, Sharma A, Rai RR, Malhotra B. Contribution of hepatitis E virus in acute sporadic hepatitis in North western India. *Indian J Med Res* 2012; 136:477–82.
26. Sebastian B, Mathai S, Mathew G, Ouseph M, Balakrishnan P. An outbreak of hepatitis A in central India: changing patterns. *Indian J Gastroenterol* 2001; 20:132–5.
27. Davaalkham D, Enkhoyun T, Takahashi M, Nakamura Y, Okamoto H. Hepatitis A and E virus infections among children in Mongolia. *Am J Trop Med Hygiene* 2009; 81:248–51.
28. Arankalle VA, Sarada devi KL, Lole KS, Shenoy KT, Verma V, Haneephani M. Molecular characterization of hepatitis A virus from a large outbreak from Kerala, India. *Indian J Med Res* 2006; 123:760–9

29. Rath CP, Akki A, Patil S V, Kalyanshetkar SS. Seroprevalence of Hepatitis A Virus Antibody in Bijapur, Karnataka. *Indian Pediatr*
30. Ahmed M, Munshi S, Nessa A, Ullah M, Tabassum S, Islam M. High prevalence of hepatitis A virus antibody among Bangladeshi children and young adults warrants pre-immunization screening of antibody in HAV vaccination strategy. *Indian J Med Microbiol*
31. Samaddar A, Taklikar S, Kale P, Kumar C, Baveja S. Infectious hepatitis: A 3-year retrospective study at a tertiary care hospital in India. *Indian J Med Microbiol*. 2019;37(2):230–4.
32. Bansal Y, Singla N, Garg K, Sharma G. Seroprevalence of hepatitis A and hepatitis E in patients at a teaching hospital of northern India over a period of 8 years. *J Fam Med Prim Care*
33. Priyadarshini J, Katara R, Vadsmiya M, Vegad MM. Seroprevalence of HAV and HEV Infection in Patients Suspected Of Acute Viral Hepatitis. *Natl J Integr Res Med*. 2017;8(2):88–90.
34. Kumar M, Kumar R, Sahoo A, Duggal N. Prevalence of Hepatitis A Virus (HAV) and Hepatitis E Virus (HEV) in the Patients Presenting with Acute Viral Hepatitis (AVH) in a Tertiary Care Hospital Manoj. *J Commun Dis*. 2017;49(3):57–60.